

ENERGY DATA AND AUTOMATION ARCHITECTURE

DELIVERABLE D3.3

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SHORT ABSTRACT	This deliverable provides an overview of the running demonstrations for the energy vertical. The demonstration is deployed at the construction, robotics and energy testbed.
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Executive Summary

Within the TARGET-X project, the integration of 5G in the energy, construction, manufacturing, and automotive verticals is evaluated. The goal is to identify already available features and possible features for 6G that can benefit these verticals. The energy vertical targets mainly the topics of monitoring, energy awareness and consumption. The developed software and hardware are not only used for grid-specific use cases, but also in other verticals to evaluate the energy consumption of a specific process.

This deliverable provides the Link to the public repository for the software architecture within the energy vertical. The software contains the components needed for Raspberry PI operating system image generation, as well as the backend components that are used for management and visualization of the data acquired by the field devices.

Table of Contents

- DISCLAIMER1**
- EXECUTIVE SUMMARY3**
- TABLE OF CONTENTS.....4**
- LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS.....5**
- 1 INTRODUCTION.....6**
 - 1.1 RELATION TO OTHER ACTIVITIES.....6
- 2 SOFTWARE STACK7**
- 3 REFERENCES8**

Document: Energy data and automation architecture

Dissemination level: Public

Date: 2024-12-16

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

5G 5th Generation

6G 6th Generation

1 Introduction

Within the TARGET-X project, the 5G energy vertical is strongly focused on monitoring and energy awareness. This is especially important for the low voltage grid, where, until now, monitoring is not too common. Especially with the increase in volatile energy sources which are often deployed in the low voltage grid, a better understanding is key for a stable operation in the future. To achieve this goal, a major component needed is a 5G-enabled software and hardware architecture.

This deliverable provides the link to the publicly available software architecture.

1.1 Relation to other activities

This deliverable describes the software architecture for the energy awareness and grid monitoring use cases. The use cases are run in the energy, robotics and construction testbed, and therefore a strong relation to WP2 (Robotics) and WP5 (Construction) is present.

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2 Software Stack

The software is published via the RWTH Gitlab environment. The architecture comprises different software components that are continuously extended. A detailed description of components can be found in Deliverable 3.4 [1].

Repository URL:

<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/acs/public/open-energy-data-platform>

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3 References

- [1] D3.4 Energy Data and Automation Architecture Report